

TWINNING FOR PROMOTING EXCELLENCE, ABILITY AND KNOWLEDGE TO DEVELOP ADVANCED WASTE GASIFICATION SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT: The H2020 project TWIN-PEAKS emphasises on promoting excellence and knowledge to develop advanced waste gasification solutions as well as incorporating power-to-X concept (PtX) by establishing a research and innovation collaboration between Lithuanian Energy Institute (LEI, Lithuania), Vytautas Magnus University (VDU, Lithuania), Technical University of Munich (TUM, Germany), Chalmers University of Technology (CTH, Sweden), and WIP (Germany). The final goal is to raise the scientific excellence, capacities and international reputation of LEI and VMU in these respective fields. This will be achieved by the planned project activities, such as training, summer schools, conference and outreach events, dedicated for early-stage and advanced researchers. One of the key activities and milestones is the adoption of a joint research strategy between project partners, which is based on three research pillars: (plasma-enhanced) gasification processes, (plasma-assisted) methanation and feedstocks and utilization pathways. The strategy fully reflects the aims and goals of Lithuania and European Union, which are defined in Lithuania's National Energy Independence Strategy, a national law on the Usage of Alternative Fuels and European Green Deal, including circular economy and climate change initiatives and ambitions. A short outlook regarding the current situation and perspectives in waste-to-energy and power-to-X in Lithuania is also described. Finally, a short description on how the adopted research strategy may contribute to the achievement of the goals defined in national and EU initiatives is also provided.

Keywords: gasification, syngas, thermochemical conversion, waste.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lithuania is slowly advancing in economic, technological and sustainable development in the field of Waste-to-Energy (WtE) as well as Power-to-X (PtX), especially in processing of waste, when it is not suitable to be recovered or recycled into alternative renewable fuels and hydrogen. This will be mostly done by sorting at Mechanical and Biological waste treatment (MBT) plants and municipal solid waste incineration plants. Waste (municipal solid waste, MSW), refuse derived fuels (RDF), solid recovered fuels (SRF), various types of biomass, not suitable for recycling or recovering but still having energetic value, can be successfully utilised for energy, fuels or chemicals production via thermochemical pathway. So far, two MSW incineration plants have been in operation in Lithuania (in Klaipėda and Kaunas). One more MSW incineration plant is under commissioning in Vilnius. Therefore, some highly qualified specialists and engineers will be required to maintain their operation. Moreover, new more advanced thermochemical conversion technologies, e.g. plasma gasification, has to be developed in order to manage waste in a more sustainable way instead of direct waste incineration. Additionally, the PtX concept, especially power-to-methane, should be enhanced from the laboratory to industrial scale. This can only be ensured through the periodic trainings, skills development and knowledge exchange, which Lithuania Energy Institute researchers can provide.

2 THE TWIN-PEAKS PROJECT

The EU project TWIN-PEAKS (H2020;

www.twinpeaks-h2020.eu) aims to establish a research and innovation collaboration between Lithuanian Energy Institute (LEI), Vytautas Magnus University (VDU), Technical University of Munich (TUM), Chalmers University of Technology (CTH) and WIP to raise the scientific excellence, capacities and international reputation of LEI and VMU in advanced waste gasification. To support the contribution of Lithuania to the EU's low-carbon economy roadmap, LEI and VMU plan to establish an association to foster the uptake of WtE as well as PtX innovation in Lithuania and engage the country in pan-European collaborative efforts on this topic. This association will be based on research-supported initiatives to guide policies and support businesses. To ensure its success, both institutions need to increase their research excellence in the strategic priority topic of waste gasification and power-to-X and develop international networks.

The existing research infrastructure at each project partner's site will be utilized to perform a joint experimental research in each research priority identified. Within the project, TUM operates entrained flow gasifier and synthesis gas cleaning and conditioning rigs and CTH has fluidized bed lab reactor for bench scale experiments and kinetic investigation. A downdraft gasifier coupled with plasma treatment and a plasma gasification unit alone are run at LEI site WtX and PtX processes. Project partners, WIP and VMU, will support with soft skills and methods regarding socio-economic aspects, technology acceptance and IPR protection issues.

Each partner with specific research expertise will share his knowledge in the respective field and obtain the new one. As a result, this opens new horizons for joint research activities to perform experiments during staff exchanges, prepare joint scientific publications from the

experimental results obtained, and apply for new research grants.

By assisting LEI and VMU to improve their research and innovation excellence, reputation, networks, attractiveness and funding, the TWIN-PEAKS project will provide Lithuania with a strong research base in WtE and PtX. This will help Lithuania to increase the effectiveness of its measures for the transition to sustainable energy, especially to reach Paris Agreement's objectives and the goals of the Lithuanian National Energy Independence Strategy.

3 ACHIEVEMENTS AND PERSPECTIVES IN WASTE-TO-ENERGY AND POWER-TO-X IN LITHUANIA

This chapter summarises a short introduction on the current situation and perspectives in WtE and PtX in Lithuania.

During the Soviet times and between the time Lithuania regained its independence in the 1990s and its acceptance to the EU in 2004, almost 100% of waste was deposited in landfills with no intention on reusing, recycling, composting or converting to energy. The situation changed after Lithuania's acceptance to the EU in 2004. Despite growth in municipal solid waste (MSW) generation (365 kg per capita in 2000 to 472 kg per capita in 2019), Lithuania has reduced significantly the share of MSW deposited in landfills (Fig. 1). Nowadays, annual waste generation by all economic activities and households in Lithuania amounts to 6.2 million tonnes. Around 4.5 million tonnes of generated waste are treated [1].

Figure 1: Comparison of waste treatment by sectors in selected countries. [1]

The Landfill EU Directive (1999/31/EC) obliges Member States to reduce the amount of biodegradable municipal waste that they landfill by 35% of the 1995 levels by 2016 (for some countries by 2020). Lithuania has set the target to reduce the percentage of waste disposed in landfills to 35% by 2020, simultaneously increasing the share of recovering, recycling and incineration. By 2030, waste disposed in landfills should account for not more than 5%.

Recycling and WtE are essential and complimentary pillars of an integrated waste management system that are usually mistakenly opposed to each other. The solid waste management hierarchy in the EU (Directive 2008/98/EC) ranks the most environmentally-sound strategies from MSW treatment to protect the environment and human health, which shall be applied in the following order: prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery (including WtE), and safe disposal in sanitary landfills as a last option. Although the ultimate goal of a

perfect waste management system is to recover all recyclable materials, it is a fact that the recycling chain presents significant technical, social and economic barriers. It is estimated that a virtuous recycling system would still produce up to 60% of rejects that would need a final destination, with WtE ranking way before landfilling in the waste management hierarchy [2]. It can be readily appreciated, therefore, that both recycling and WtE are complimentary in their role to divert MSW from landfills, thus complying with the priority order of European directives.

The conventional way to generate electricity from waste is through direct combustion, with the heat used to produce steam to drive a turbine. This is indirect generation with an overall efficiency of 15-27%. Gasification instead produces a combustible synthesis gas (often abbreviated to syngas), which can either be used for direct generation in a gas turbine or engine (more efficient than steam turbine), or converted in clean, largely renewable, drop-in fuels and chemicals (e.g. biodiesel, bioSNG, biomethanol, methane, etc.), which displace the fossil counterparts thus contributing to decarbonising a large part of the current energy sector.

In this sense, direct incineration or combined heat and power (CHP) production from waste represent a step forward in the waste management hierarchy compared to landfill, however is not as sustainable as the production of higher-added value fuels or chemicals that gasification would offer. Therefore, gasification is considered as an advanced method over direct incineration, and better placed to meet the circular economy approach, as recommended by EU directives. Despite the clear advantages, gasification of waste is still in the development phase, starting from waste characterisation to technological application and industrialisation as well as economics. Nevertheless, according to EU directives, national laws, the Paris Agreement, many countries put a lot of effort on the development of gasification technologies, especially the ones enabling to produce the best quality syngas, such as plasma gasifiers, followed by new-generation entrained flow (EF), dual, circulating fluidised bed (CFB) and bubbling fluidised bed (BFB) gasifiers.

There are more than 272 operating gasification plants worldwide with 686 gasifiers. Currently, 74 plants are under construction worldwide that will have a total of 238 gasifiers and produce 83 MWth. Worldwide gasification capacity is expected to grow significantly by 2021, mostly based on coal and natural gas as a primary feedstock. While biomass and waste feed is currently very small, this feedstock category is expected to grow in the future. So far, Europe is a leader in the development of biomass/waste gasifiers [3].

So far, two MSW incineration plants have been in operation in Lithuania (in Klaipėda since 2013 and Kaunas since 2020). The treatment capacity of the plant in Klaipėda is 255,000 tonnes per year (180,000 tonnes of MSW, including waste derived fuels (RDF), the rest 75,000 tonnes is biomass). Thermal and electrical power capacity of the plant is 65 MW and 21 MW, respectively [4]. The CHP plant in Kaunas was designed to treat approx. 200,000 tonnes of MSW generated in the region. The plant's thermal and electrical capacity exceeds 70 MW and 26 MW, respectively [5]. The third most powerful MSW incineration plant is under commissioning in Vilnius. It is designed to operate on biomass and waste. Thermal and electrical power of the

plant is 240 MW (~60 MW from waste) and 100 MW (~20 MW from waste), respectively [6]. Currently no commercial gasifiers are under operation in Lithuania. The fundamental and applied research in this field, including plasma assisted gasification, is only concentrated at research institutes, mostly LEI, and to some extent at universities. However, more advanced waste treatment methods, like gasification, are now on a table at the European level, because of the political will to exclude carbon dioxide emissions originating from direct waste incineration as a carbon dioxide neutral process. Therefore, in order to keep up with the rest EU Member states, especially pan-leaders from Germany, Sweden, etc., Lithuania will need to invest into development of more advanced and innovative waste treatment methods instead of direct waste incineration. Such knowledge and experience accumulated at LEI and VMU could help to internally use and even export such technologies taking into account the whole value-chain from technological point of view to socio-economical.

Power-to-X concept is very new in Lithuania. Research is only performed at laboratory scale at research institutes and universities. However, a huge interest from industry has arisen to utilize green hydrogen in their technological processes, e.g. chemical fertilizers producers, and even national electrical and gas grid operators to balance grid due to unstable power generation by renewables (wind, solar, hydro) or to directly inject hydrogen into main gas grids, thus replacing dependence on natural gas. Moreover, recently a national law on the usage on alternative fuels in transportation sector has been approved by the Lithuanian Parliament. One of the goals of the law is that biomethane and green hydrogen together should comprise not less than 5% of the total energy consumption in transportation sector by 2030. Therefore, technological development of biomethane and green hydrogen technologies (electrolyse, fuel cells, methanation, etc.) will definitely be one of the state's priorities. So, LEI's experience and knowledge obtained within the TWIN-PEAKS project implementation and beyond should have a great impact on further Lithuania's technological advances and development in this respective field.

4 TWIN-PEAKS PROJECT RESULTS & ITS REALATION TO NATIONAL AND EU AIMS

The TWIN-PEAKS project is running since October 2020 and the very first results are mostly based on the joint Research Strategy adopted between the project partners. Nevertheless, the identified joint research priorities also contribute to national and Europe's goals and vision.

Based on a joint Research Strategy adopted between the project partners, three strategic research priorities have been identified for further joint scientific activities (Fig. 2):

- (Plasma-enhanced) gasification processes,
- (Plasma-assisted) methanation,
- Feedstocks and utilization pathways.

The expression in parentheses in a) and b) identified research activities includes not only the use of plasma method but also its coupling with more conventional gasification and methanation methods. Moreover, besides

some knowledge in the downdraft gasification accumulated at LEI, a deeper understanding of fundamental processes occurring in the fluidized bed and entrained flow gasification available at CTH and TUM is also of great interest. The same stands for the understanding of fundamentals of conventional methanation process, reactors and process optimization as well as plasma-assisted methanation.

Figure 2: Waste gasification process chain as basis for identification of research priorities

(Plasma-enhanced) gasification processes: This research priority focuses on the utilization of thermal plasmas as allothermal heat sources for gasification processes. In this regard, both fundamental level research and applied research needs to be undertaken. Fundamental level research will need to focus on the effect plasma has on the gasification reaction parameters such as particle size, surface areas, etc., as well as the reactions taking place between solid fuels and the plasma. Applied research will have to entail the utilization of the thermal plasma in the gasification process itself and the assessment of thermal plasma for gas cleaning purposes.

(Plasma-assisted) methanation: This research priority includes the assessment of the application of a non-thermal plasma on different kinds of methanation reactor configurations as well as on increasing catalyst activity. Furthermore, the possibility of donating hydrogen via plasma will need to be assessed. Finally, this priority also includes a potential transfer of the learnings for the usage of plasma for methanation to other reactions/syntheses coupling with PtX concept.

Feedstocks and utilization pathways: As part of this research priority, potential feedstocks for a plasma-enhanced gasification process chain need to be evaluated and required pre-treatments investigated to identify most suitable feedstocks and input pathways. In addition, possible utilization pathways need to be assessed for the gasification products. This includes electricity generation options such as traditional combustion routes and fuel cell processes as well as syntheses into base chemicals for usage as inputs for the chemical industry (e.g., Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, etc.).

Figure 3: Mapping of identified strategic research priorities across waste gasification value-chain. Light grey indicates coverage by respective research priority.

The three research priorities, hence, cover the whole waste gasification process chain are presented in Fig. 3. Therefore, the research priorities can form the basis for the development of a complete (plasma-assisted) waste gasification process for potential future commercialization of the technology(s). Moreover, the above reported research directions fully complies with Lithuania's National Energy Independence Strategy goals as well as Lithuanian Government's and EC's aims defined in the European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Climate change initiatives and ambitions [7].

To strengthen technological aspects defined in the strategy and thus making the project consortium more diverse and interdisciplinary, the support from VMU and WIP with soft-skills is crucial at any point of view. Such skills include but are not limited to:

- Value drivers/Value proposition building;
- Value based business model building/Support schemes;
- Marketing decisions (awareness raising, value proposition/evidence-based communication etc.);
- Value proposition/innovation perception (communication response assessment etc.);
- Socio-economic impact (of sociotechnical innovations; on social justice, energy poverty, inequality);
- Dissemination, exploitation and communication, etc.

Based on the planned joint research activities, the preliminary Horizon Europe work programme formed the major basis for the identification of potentially attractive funding opportunities. Initially, all European calls were collected that fit the research focus areas 1 to 3. These calls were then ranked according to their attractiveness for the consortium. Grant applications are planned to be initiated and submitted.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Despite the type of the TWIN-PEAKS project classified as a coordination and support action as well as other planned 'soft' activities to be done, in the upcoming two and a half years, the TWIN-PEAKS consortium will keep working on the research priorities defined in the Research Strategy adopted by all project partners. Moreover, the cooperation between project partners will also last beyond the period of the project implementation.

6 REFERENCES

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8 TWIN-PEAKS PROJECT LOGO

Project partners logos:

